

INDICATIONS OF THE MORPHOMETRIC CHANGES OF THE THYMUSIS IN INFANTS WHO DIED IN THE ANTENATAL PERIOD

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Abstract: Delays in morphological development in the pituitary gland: the cortical layer of the thymus is characterized by the fact that it occupies a very small area of the medulla in terms of width, and there are almost no lymphocytes. As the main morphological substrate of these changes, the size of the reticuloepithelial cells of the thymus cortical layer is small, the desmasomas are short and thick, the number of sparse fibrous structures connecting the spaces of desmasomas, and the perivascular areas of the cortical layer are numerous. Those who died from intrauterine infection in the antenatal period make up 78.2% of all babies and form the basis of our research.

Key words: thymus, immunohistochemistry, involution, immunodeficiency, necrosis, apoptosis.

The relevance of the problem: It is understood that premature birth of the fetus due to intrauterine infection is 1-4% of every 1000 births in the world of newborns or perinatal pathologies. It is the development of the immune system that has a major impact on health, especially during pregnancy, early childhood, and even throughout life (Hertz-Picciotto et al., 2008). There is increasing evidence revealing a link between interventions during the perinatal period and immune system disorders in offspring in postnatal life (Yang et al., 2014) . In perinatal pathologies, antenatal death mainly develops together with infectious and non-infectious etiological processes and manifests itself in the form of fetal immaturity, asphyxia, birth trauma, pneumopathies, perinatal blood circulation disorders in the brain, and hemorrhagic disease of newborns.

Discussion and results: Morphological and immunohistochemical methods of thymus tissue of stillborn babies in the antenatal period were used. The prepared micropreparation was measured by mathematical calculation of the size, width, and area of fibrous structures in 200x magnified field of view using NanoZoomer (REF C13140-21.S/N000198/HAMAMATSU PHOTONICS/431-3196 JAPAN) Hamamatsu (QuPath-0.4.0, NanoZoomer Digital Pathology Image) through morphometric software indicators (in μm) and was

performed by calculating the mean statistical analysis. The numerical and indicator values obtained in this process were statistically and mathematically analyzed and expressed through reliability level indicators.

Thus, it can be concluded that out of 131 cases, grade 3 dysplastic coxarthrosis was detected in 73.9%, and grade 2 dysplastic coxarthrosis in 26.7%, and it was found that dysplastic coxarthrosis of the 3rd degree was the most common. According to the morphometric indicators of the thymus gland of stillborn babies of different periods of 23-38 weeks, thymus tissue prepared from autopsy materials of antenatally dead babies at 23-36 weeks was scanned in NanoZoomer. At least 10 sections were taken from each case, and average sizes were obtained with a confidence index of no less than $R \leq 0.01$, with an average error of 5 μm lost between consecutive sections. The main aspects were the structural aspects of the thymus: cells, fibrous structures, the thickness of the bark and medulla layers, the area occupied by each of these structures, and other indicators were obtained. Specifically, the ratio of spaces in the parenchyma of the thymus in the spatial dimensions to the cellular content was on average 5/3, and signs of collapse were found in 40% of the stroma. This confirms the accidental transformation of the thymus and premature involution of the thymus. According to different indicators of the anatomical layers of the thymus at different periods of the gestational period, at 22-27 weeks, the thickness of the cortical layer was on average $54.4 \pm 0.4 \mu\text{m}$, in the control group this indicator was $58.3 \pm 0.5 \mu\text{m}$, and statistical reliability It was shown by the lack of relative differences in terms of the indicator. The cortical layer of the thymus of babies who died antenatally at 28-33 weeks is $141.19 \pm 1.11 \mu\text{m}$, and the cortical layer of the thymus of the control group of the same period is $67.12 \pm 1.12 \mu\text{m}$, and the differences are statistically significant in the ratio of 2:1. confirms that the thymus is lagging behind in development.

References used:

1. Biloshapka V. A. i dr. Modern aspects of pathomorphology of congenital cytomegalovirus infection in children in the first year of life (a practical case) // Mediko-sotsialnye problemy semi. - 2021. - T. 26. - no. 2. - S. 99-104.
2. Borodin, Yu.I. Peripheral lymphoid structure: formation and function / Yu.I. Borodin, O.V. Gorchakova, V.N. Gorchakov // Morphology. - 2016. - T. 150, No. 4.- S.90-96.
3. Bocharova O.A., Karpova R.V., Bocharov E.V., Vershinskaya A.A., dr. b2-integrin LFA-1, MAC-1 - a target for the improvement of immunity against tumors. // Russian biotherapeutic journal. 2020;19(1):53-8.

4. Bosin V.Yu., Verbitskaya A.I., Solomin Yu.A. Sravnitel'naya otsenka dannykh ultrazhenkovogo i sektsionnogo issledovaniya vilochkovoy zhelelyu detey //Ultrazvukovaya diagnostika v akusherstve, gynecelokii i pediatrii. No. 3.S. 40-47.
5. Bubnova N. V. i dr. Izmenenie kletochnogo sostava thymus krysa cherez 90 dney posle vvedeniya uretana na fone priema selena //Journal anatomii i histopatologii. - 2024. - T. 13. – no. 1. – S. 19-27.
6. Verbitskaya A.I., Solokhin Yu.A., Nazarova N.F. Osobennosti echografii vilochkovoy zhelelyu u detey v lichnye razrastnye periody //Ultrazvukovaya i funktsionalnaya diagnostika. 2001. No. 3. S. 34-39.
7. Volkov V.G., Kastor M.V. Sovremennye vzglyady na problemu klassifikatsii i opredeleniya prichin mertvorozdeniya // Rossiyskiy vestnik akushera-gynecologia. 2020. T. 20. No. 3. S. 29-3.
8. Galeeva E.N. Kharakternye osobennosti stanovlenii topografii ryada organov immunnnoi sistemy chyloveka v rannem peltnom periode ontogeneza // Vestnik novykh meditsinskikh tekhnologiy, 2011. T. 18 No. 2. S. 489-492.
9. Galeeva E. N. Morphological characteristics of the functional zone of the thymus of a human being in the middle reproductive period of ontogeny // Orenburg medical journal. - 2015. - T. 3. – no. 2 (10). - S. 15-19.

